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Research

Clinical study of Perioperative Use of Levosimendan in Patients Undergoing Heart Valve Replacement

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Email: txjnuph@126.com**Abstract:**

Objective To investigate the clinical effect of levosimendan in perioperative aortic and/or mitral valve replacement. **Methods** Patients undergoing open heart aortic and/or mitral valve replacement in our hospital from January 2018 to December 2019 were enrolled. 45 patients in the control group received routine perioperative treatment based on dopamine, while 45 patients in the research group received continuous perioperative administration of levosimendan injection for 24h on the basis of routine treatment. The left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF), left ventricular end-diastolic diameter (LVDd) and left ventricular end-systolic diameter (LVDs) were evaluated by color doppler echocardiography before and one week after surgery. Postoperative mechanical ventilation weaning time, length of ICU stays, number of vasoactive drugs used and withdrawal time; indexes of liver and kidney function before and on the day after surgery to 10 days after surgery; use of in vitro support techniques such as aortic balloon pulsation (IABP), continuous renal replacement therapy (CRRT) and extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO) within 5 days of perioperative period. **Results** The improvement of LVDs and LVEF in the study group using levosimendan one week after the operation was significantly better than that in the control group (P value was 0.013 and 0.001, respectively), and fewer kinds of vasoactive drugs were needed (P<0.001), and the risk of postoperative AKI in the study group was significantly lower than that in the control group (P=0.047). **Conclusion** The perioperative use of levosimendan can effectively promote the recovery of cardiac systolic function and reduce the risk of postoperative AKI.

Key words Levosimendan; Cardiac valve replacement; Aortic valve replacement; Mitral valve replacement; Perioperative.

INTRODUCTION

Low Cardiac Output Syndrome (LCOS) is one of the serious complications of Cardiac surgery, which can lead to acute organ injury, acute heart failure and even death ¹. In order to prevent and reduce the occurrence of LCOS, positive inotropic drugs are often used in perioperative period to improve the ventricular function of patients after cardiopulmonary bypass (CPB). However, positive inotropic drugs may increase the oxygen consumption of the myocardium and lead to myocardial ischemia, resulting in myocardial injury and arrhythmia, and increase the mortality rate and the incidence of major postoperative complications. Levosimendan, a calcium sensitizer, combines with cardiac troponin C in a calcium-ion concentration-dependent manner to produce a positive inotropic effect. It can

enhance the myocardial contractility without affecting the diastolic function. Meanwhile, it can generate the vasodilation effect by opening the ATP-sensitive K channel, so as to make the coronary artery resistance vessels and vein volume vessels relax, thus improving the coronary blood supply and reducing the anteroposterior load. Studies have confirmed that levosimendan has strong cardiac, antipyretic and antiischemic effects on patients with heart failure²⁻⁴, revealing the prospect of its application in perioperative period of cardiac surgery. We used a retrospective cohort study to investigate the efficacy of perioperative levosimendan in order to provide clinical evidence for clinical use.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY OBJECT AND CRITERIA

During the period from January 2018 to December 2019, 90 patients underwent open heart aortic valve replacement and/or mitral valve replacement in our hospital, with 45 patients in the study group and the control group respectively. The control group received routine perioperative treatment based on dopamine, while the research group received 24h continuous perioperative administration with levosimendan injection on the basis of routine treatment. Exclusion criteria: preoperative systolic blood pressure <90mmHg or patients with moderate to severe hepatic and renal insufficiency.

TREATMENT PROTOCOL

In the study group, patients were given levosimendan after the ascending aorta was opened, with the initial load dose of 12 g/kg and intravenous infusion time of 10min. The initial load dose was maintained at 0.1 g/kg/min, and then increased to 0.2 g/kg/min if the patients were well tolerated, and the intravenous infusion continued for 24 hours.

OUTCOME MEASURES

The left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF), left ventricular end-diastolic diameter (LVDD) and left ventricular end-systolic diameter (LVDS) were evaluated by color doppler echocardiography before and one week after surgery. Data extraction included postoperative mechanical ventilation weaning time, custody detention time, number of vasoactive drugs used and withdrawal time, and indexes of liver and kidney function before and on the day after surgery to 10 days after surgery. Use of *in vitro* support techniques such as aortic balloon pulsation (IABP), continuous renal replacement therapy (CRRT) and extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO) within 5 days of perioperative period were also assessed.

Perioperative Acute Kidney Injury (AKI) was divided into three levels according to KDIGO standard: serum creatinine (Scr) increased by 1.5-1.9 times of the baseline value or ≥ 26.5 Kidney mol/L, or urine volume <0.5ml/(kg/h) lasted for 6-12h, which was defined as level 1. Scr reached 2.0-2.9 times of the base value, or urine volume <0.5ml/(kg/h) lasted ≥ 12 h, which was defined as level 2. Scr reached 3 times or more of the base value, or the absolute value increased ≥ 353.6 mol/L, or began renal replacement therapy, or the urine volume <0.3ml/(kg/h) lasted ≥ 24 h or no urine ≥ 12 h, which was defined as level 3. The ALI criteria of the modified international Acute Liver Failure Study Group (ALFSG) were as follows: ALT increased > 10 times normal value and TBil > 3 times normal value within 5 days after surgery. Abnormal Liver Function Test (aLFT) was defined as an elevation of ALT and/or TBil greater than 2 times normal value 5 d after surgery. Due to the use of perioperative anticoagulants, the international standardized ratio of prothrombin time (INR)>1.5 was not included⁵.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

SPSS 16.0 statistical software was used for data processing. T test was used for quantitative data. The Chi Square Test was used for comparison of non-grade qualitative data. When the number of samples was more than 40 but the theoretical frequency was more than 1 and less than 5, the corrected chi square test was used. When the theoretical frequency of occurrence is

less than 1, Fisher's Exact Test is used. The rank data were tested by the rank sum test. $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

STUDY CHARACTERISTICS

45 patients were included in the study group and 45 patients in the control group. There was no significant difference in the basic characteristics of the two groups ($P > 0.05$), such as age, gender, history of complicated diseases, types of surgery, length of operation, duration of cardiopulmonary bypass (CPB) and aortic cross-clamp time (**Table 1**).

Table 1 Baseline demographic data of the patients.

	Study Group (N=45)	Control Group (N=45)	P Value
Male	22 (48.9%)	20 (44.4%)	0.673
Age	60.53±8.54	57.47±13.44	0.200
BMI/ kg/m²	21.92±3.01	22.32±2.98	0.526
Smoking	8 (17.8%)	5 (11.1%)	0.368
Type 2 Diabetes	3 (6.7%)	5 (11.1%)	0.714
History of Cerebrovascular Disease	9 (20.0%)	4 (8.9%)	0.134
History of COPD	4 (8.9%)	4 (8.9%)	1.000
Hypertension			0.779
No	28 (62.2%)	26 (57.8%)	
Grade 1	6 (13.3%)	4 (8.9%)	
Grade 2	6 (13.3%)	8 (17.8%)	
Grade 3	5 (11.1%)	7 (15.6%)	
NYHA Functional Classification			0.241
Class II	14 (31.1%)	21 (46.7%)	
Class III	23 (51.1%)	20 (44.4%)	
Class IV	8 (17.8%)	4 (8.9%)	
Types of Surgery			0.469
Aortic valve replacement	19 (42.2%)	14 (31.1%)	
Mitral valve replacement	9 (20.0%)	13 (28.9%)	
Aortic and Mitral valve replacement	17 (37.8%)	18 (40.0%)	
Length of Operation/h	5.56±1.42	5.17±2.05	0.294
Duration of CPB/min	173.86±50.53	160.15±88.67	0.464
Aortic Cross-Clamp Time /min	110.71±32.83	104.71±61.03	0.637

IMPROVEMENT OF LEFT VENTRICULAR FUNCTION

One week after the operation, the LVEF of the two groups increased compared with that before the operation, and the improvement degree of the study group was significantly higher than that of the control group ($P = 0.013$). The LVDD and LVDs of the two groups decreased postoperatively, and there was no statistical difference between the groups. The reduction of LVDs in the study group was significantly larger than that in the control group ($P = 0.001$), as shown in **Table 2**.

Table 2 Left ventricular function index of the patients.

		Study Group (N=45)	Control Group (N=45)	P Value
LVEF/%	Preoperative	22 (48.9%)	60.09±9.07	0.354
	Postoperative difference from the preoperative value	5.13±9.79	1.38±10.20	0.013
LVDd/mm	Preoperative	51.43±10.40	50.44±9.18	0.639
	Preoperative difference from the postoperative value	5.80±7.47	4.73±6.89	0.501
LVDs/mm	Preoperative	36.22±9.93	33.59±8.67	0.216
	Preoperative difference from the postoperative value	6.31±6.33	1.59±5.16	0.001

POSTOPERATIVE WEANING TIME, LENGTH OF ICU STAY AND VASOACTIVE DRUG SUPPORT

In the study group and the control group, 4 and 10 patients experienced delayed withdrawal of mechanical ventilation (defined as weaning time greater than 72 hours) after surgery, but the difference between the groups was not statistically significant ($P=0.067$), as shown in **Table 3**. In the control group, the postoperative mechanical ventilation time of one patient was as long as 1203 h, and the length of ICU stay was 55.75 days. A total of 5 vasoactive drugs were used and the drugs were stopped only 34 days after the operation. Considering that these special value may affect the data distribution and statistical test, we conducted a quantitative comparison of the two groups of patients' weaning time and length of ICU stay before and after excluding the special value of the case. It was found that after excluding the special value, the patients in the study group tended to be shorter weaning time than those in the control group, but there was no statistical difference ($P=0.057$). And there was no significant difference in the length of ICU stay between the two groups either. In addition, no matter whether the special values were excluded or not, the number of varieties of vasoactive drugs used in patients in the study group was significantly less than that in the control group ($P<0.001$), and the discontinuation time was no different, as shown in **Table 4**.

Table 3 Comparison of extubation time between two groups.

	Study Group (N=45)	Control Group (N=45)	P Value
Weaning Time/h			0.067
<48	41	35	
48-71.9	4	6	
72-95.9	0	1	
≥96	0	3	

Table 4 Weaning Time, Length of ICU Stay and Vasoactive Drug Support.

	Special Values Not Excluded			Special Values Excluded		
	Study Group (N=45)	Control Group (N=45)	P value	Study Group (N=45)	Control Group (N=45)	P value
Weaning Time /h	26.19±14.52	62.91±177.03	0.172	26.19±14.52	37.00±33.98	0.057
Length of ICU Stay /d	4.58±2.49	6.28±8.57	0.203	4.58±2.49	5.16±4.11	0.420
Number of Vasoactive Drugs	2.31±0.56	3.42±0.69	<0.001	2.31±0.56	3.39±0.66	<0.001
Duration of Vasoactive Drugs Treatment /d	5.91±2.45	6.49±5.41	0.512	5.91±2.45	5.87±3.46	0.948

USE OF SUPPORT TECHNIQUE AND PERIOPERATIVE ACUTE LIVER / KIDNEY INJURY

None of the patients in this study used ECMO, and there was no significant difference in postoperative IABP utilization between the two groups ($P=0.725$). No patients in the study

group required CRRT treatment, while 1 patient in the control group began to use CRRT on the first day after surgery due to oliguria caused by LCOS. The statistical results indicated that the risk of AKI in the study group was significantly lower than that in the control group ($P=0.047$). There was no statistical difference in the incidence of postoperative liver dysfunction between the two groups ($P=0.234$), as shown in **Table 5**.

Table 5 IABP Using and Perioperative Acute Injury of Liver and Kidney Function.

	Study Group (N=45)	Control Group (N=45)	P Value
IABP	5	4	0.725
AKI			0.047
Level 1	8	12	
Level 2	1	2	
Level 3	0	3	
Postoperative Liver dysfunction			0.234
aLFT	2	4	
ALI	0	1	

DISCUSSION

Patients with severe heart valve disease are one of the main subjects of cardiac surgery. The serious lesions of mitral valve and aortic valve caused by various causes lead to the deterioration of cardiac hemodynamics, which seriously affects the quality of life and survival of patients. While addressing cardiac valve problems in patients, cardiac surgery is multifaceted, involving sympathetic activation, inflammatory response, hemodynamic changes, and so on, and may therefore exacerbate cardiac dysfunction. Postoperative low cardiac output syndrome (LCOS) is one of the potentially life-threatening serious complications^{1,6}. The mortality rate of patients with LCOS can be as high as 16.9% (compared with 0.9% of patients without LCOS)⁶. Preoperative left ventricular dysfunction was a major risk factor for LCOS^{7,8}. Low perfusion caused by low cardiac output can damage other organ functions, such as acute kidney injury, and seriously lead to acute heart failure, resulting in increased long-term postoperative mortality^{9,10}.

Positive inotropic drugs such as dopamine, dobutamine, epinephrine, and milrinone are often used to improve ventricular function after CPB during the perioperative period of cardiac surgery. However, while these drugs increase the myocardial contractility, they will increase the oxygen consumption of the myocardium, which leads to myocardial ischemia. They may also cause the imbalance of calcium balance, which leads to the abnormal increase of intracellular calcium concentration, namely calcium overload, leading to the increased incidence of arrhythmia and the irreversible damage in the cell, and accelerate the death of cardiac cells. This makes the application of positive inotropic drugs in cardiac surgery controversial. Studies have shown that perioperative and postoperative use of positive inotropic drugs can increase the mortality rate and the incidence of major postoperative complications¹¹. Therefore, it is very important to improve cardiac function and reduce the use of vasoactive drugs as soon as possible after the surgery. A drug that can improve cardiac function without significantly increasing the oxygen consumption of the myocardium is needed.

According to the consensus of experts published in the International Journal of Cardiology in 2015¹², the use of the calcium sensitizer levosimendan in patients undergoing cardiac surgery can increase myocardial contractility without increasing myocardial oxygen consumption, and have cardioprotective, antihypertensive and antiischemic effects. Although three large randomized controlled trials published in recent years examined the outcome of using levosimendan in the perioperative period of cardiac surgery and obtained neutral results¹³⁻¹⁵, a number of recent meta-analyses evaluating the effect of levosimendan in cardiac surgery

patients with or without systolic dysfunction all found that the incidence of mortality and all other adverse outcomes (such as postoperative renal failure requiring dialysis, atrial fibrillation, myocardial injury, etc.) decreased significantly in the levosimendan treatment group, and the patients with reduced LVEF benefited the most¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

In this study, most of the included patients had severe mitral valve and/or aortic valve lesions, so although the average LVEF of the patients was 58-60% under the evaluation of color doppler ultrasound, the pulmonary congestion and systemic circulation congestion caused by hemodynamic disorders caused more severe symptoms of heart failure such as dyspnea and peripheral edema. The results indicated that the improvement of left ventricular systolic function and ejection fraction in the study group using levosimendan one week after the operation was significantly better than that in the control group, and fewer kinds of vasoactive drugs were needed, which confirmed the good promoting effect of levosimendan on the recovery of cardiac function after the operation. Cardiac insufficiency are independent risk factors for postoperative weaning failure¹⁹, and patients with long-term mechanical ventilation can cause increased risk of postoperative infection and influence prognosis²⁰. Through comparison, we found that the perioperative use of levosimendan had a trend of shortening the postoperative mechanical ventilation time of patients, which was consistent with the results of some published reports²¹⁻²³, but the difference was not statistically significant. The lack of positive significance may be related to the fact that preoperative LVEF was not lower than 40% in all patients included in this study.

In terms of postoperative renal injury, among the 90 cases of patients in the two groups observed in this study, 27 cases developed AKI, with an incidence of 28.89%. Most of the cases presented with increased creatinine and the degree was mainly mild (20 cases with grade 1 AKI, accounting for 74.07%). The risk of postoperative AKI in patients in the study group was significantly lower than that in the control group, suggesting that the use of levosimendan in perioperative period may be beneficial to perioperative kidney protection, which is also consistent with the previous reports.

In summary, perioperative use of levosimendan may be superior to traditional inotropic drugs in improving cardiac function and reducing the incidence of renal injury. However, due to limited conditions, this study failed to comprehensively investigate the postoperative cardiac output index and perioperative pulmonary pressure of the patients. The benefits of perioperative levosimendan on patients undergoing cardiac surgery still need to be confirmed by larger clinical trials.

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